

Automatic detection of native invasive rush species with aerial imagery and deep learning

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Summary

The expansion of native invasive rush species in British marginal upland grasslands results in decreased biodiversity and agricultural productivity. To successfully manage such species requires knowledge of their spatial distribution, which is costly to obtain using manual approaches but can be achieved efficiently using deep learning. Previous work documenting rush expansion adopted a manual approach. Here, we trained a U-Net deep convolutional neural network to automatically detect rush presence on aerial imagery in North-West England and demonstrate how it may be used to quantify change in rush cover over space and time.

KEYWORDS: rushes (*Juncus* spp.), native invasive species, deep learning, aerial imagery

1. Introduction

The expansion of invasive and native invasive plant species is a significant pressure on biodiversity and ecosystem services. Successful management to reduce these pressures requires accurate knowledge of their spatial distribution. Traditionally, this information would be collected via field survey, but the associated monetary and time expense precludes frequent and large-scale assessment.

Instead, damaging plant species can be mapped using remotely sensed imagery where there is a detectable spectral, textural, or phenological signal distinct from the surrounding vegetation. Traditional remote sensing approaches involve these signals being manually identified for input to statistical classifiers, such as random forest. Instead, deep learning bypasses manual feature extraction and can learn feature representations automatically in semantic segmentation, outperforming traditional classifiers in accuracy and computational efficiency. Deep convolutional neural networks (CNNs) learn by supervised exemplar, where both input (image) and expected output (segmented image) are provided into the network such that the spectral, textural, and geometric features can be identified to best predict an object of interest.

Rushes (*Juncus* spp.) are tussock-forming perennials, native to the British Isles, which grow rapidly in wet environments and are becoming a problem species in marginal upland grasslands. Unpalatable to livestock and expanding into dense stands that can cover entire fields, rushes reduce biodiversity and agricultural productivity. Recent work to quantify their expansion in the West Pennine Moors found an 82% increase in rush cover between 2005 and 2018 (Ashby *et al.*, 2020), thought to be related to both management and climatic factors.

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This previous work quantified rush, generally distinct from surrounding grassland by height and colour (Figure 1), through manual surveys of satellite RGB imagery. However, there is opportunity to develop a more automated, objective, and scalable approach to predicting rush presence using deep learning. Indeed, CNNs have been used to detect other plant species (Kattenborn *et al.*, 2021) but have not yet been applied to rushes. Here, we use deep learning and aerial RGB imagery to map rush cover and its change over time within a region of marginal upland grassland in North-West England.

Figure 1 (a) Ground-based photograph (October 2021) and (b) aerial RGB image (June 2021) showing the distinct height and colour contrast between rush and surrounding vegetation within improved grassland. Yellow arrow shows approximate location and direction of (a).

2. Methodology

2.1. Study area

Following Ashby *et al.* (2020) we focussed on improved grassland parcels from the UK Centre for Ecology and Hydrology (UKCEH) Land Cover Map 2021 (LCM2021; Marston *et al.*, 2021) as proxy for the marginal upland grasslands where rushes are problematic and have expanded recently. Specifically, we studied those that fall within three upland sub catchments of the River Wyre inside the Forest of Bowland Area of Outstanding Natural Beauty (n=1,078 parcels, area=32.5 km²).

2.2. Data collection and preparation

High resolution aerial RGB imagery were acquired for the study area from the EDINA Digimap service and divided into 128×128 pixel tiles (e.g., Figure 2a), keeping only those that intersect improved grassland parcels (Table 1). We semantically labelled 186 tiles of the 2021 imagery as binary rasters (e.g., Figure 2b) with the classes ‘rush’ (8% of pixels, 4,655 features) and ‘background’ (92% of pixels); where necessary, rush was distinguished from surrounding vegetation of similar nadir appearance with reference to Google Street View imagery. Image-mask pairs were then divided into subsets for model training (80%) and testing (30%) using stratified random sampling of per-tile percentage rush cover.

Table 1 Acquired imagery.

Year	Date	Images (1×1 km)	Tiles (32×32 m)	Resolution (m)	Bands	Source
2021	2021-06-02	12	34,955	0.25	RGB	Getmapping
	2021-05-30	57				
2018	2018-06-22	61	34,955	0.25	RGB	Getmapping
	2018-06-10	6				
2010	2010-04-12	69	34,955			

2.3. Model architecture and training

We implemented the U-Net CNN architecture, originally developed for biomedical image segmentation and successful with small training datasets (Ronneberger *et al.*, 2015). We modified this architecture to accommodate input arrays of size $128 \times 128 \times 3$, an image of 128×128 pixels with three channels (RGB), and outputs arrays of size $128 \times 128 \times 1$, representing probability of rush presence (e.g., Figure 2c). To increase the volume of effective training data, we augmented image-mask pairs by applying random flip, rotation, shift, and zoom operations. Models were trained for 500 epochs in the Google Colaboratory Pro Python cloud environment.

2.4. Model evaluation

We assessed model performance using F_1 score (Equation 1), the harmonic mean of precision and recall, and overall accuracy (Equation 2), calculated with counts of true positive (TP), true negative (TN), false positive (FP), and false negative (FN) pixels.

$$F_1 = 2 \cdot \frac{\textit{precision} \cdot \textit{recall}}{\textit{precision} + \textit{recall}} = \frac{2TP}{2TP + FP + FN} \quad (1)$$

$$\textit{Accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (2)$$

For overall evaluation, we placed emphasis on F_1 score as it is more robust than accuracy for datasets with high class imbalance, true here as only 8% of labelled pixels are classified as rush. To further address this challenge, we focussed accuracy calculation within the patches enclosed by bounding boxes of unique manually labelled rush features (e.g., Figure 2e) and on feature centroids (e.g., Figure 2f). By focussing within bounding boxes, we assess fewer background pixels and generate a more representative rush segmentation accuracy than produced image-wide. By evaluating feature centroids, we generate a more representative measure of ability to detect rush presence by not penalising for segmentation errors at feature edges, somewhat of a fuzzy problem at 0.25 m resolution. As a contextual metric, we also calculated the percentage difference in rush cover between mask and prediction.

We calculated accuracy and F_1 score by converting model predictions of probability of rush presence to binary presence or absence. During model training, we used the standard rounding threshold of 0.5. For performance evaluation, we analysed across a scale of thresholds.

2.5. Model prediction and analysis

We applied the trained model to predict rush presence across all acquired imagery. Model predictions were saved as georeferenced rasters and summarised at parcel-level to analyse change in rush cover between years.

Figure 2 (a–b) Image-mask pair and **(c)** corresponding model prediction from the test dataset. Prediction accuracy is highlighted using **(d)** image-wide, **(e)** bounding box (grey), and **(f)** centroid (orange) algorithms where white pixels (d and e) or green boxes (f) are *TP*, blue pixels are *FN*, and red pixels/boxes are *FP*.

3. Results and discussion

Evaluation on the independent test dataset reveals an overall F_1 score of 0.60 at a prediction threshold of 0.5, showing good performance at identifying rush (Table 1). Using our bespoke centroid and bounding box algorithms, we find good accuracy of rush detection (68%) and segmentation (63%), respectively. Across metrics, performance slightly improves with lower thresholds at the cost of greater difference between predicted and labelled rush cover. Subsequent analysis uses the threshold of 0.5, which balances good performance with small difference in predicted and labelled rush cover.

Table 2 Model performance across the test dataset.

Metric algorithm	Prediction threshold	F_1 score	Overall accuracy [%]	Difference in rush cover (prediction–mask) [%]
Image-wide	0.3	0.62 ± 0.00	97 ± 0.00	83.82 ± 12.29
	0.5	0.60 ± 0.01	97 ± 0.00	15.73 ± 6.85
	0.7	0.53 ± 0.01	97 ± 0.00	-24.12 ± 4.82
Bounding box	0.3	0.76 ± 0.01	72 ± 0.01	–
	0.5	0.65 ± 0.02	63 ± 0.01	–
	0.7	0.52 ± 0.02	52 ± 0.01	–
Centroid	0.3	0.75 ± 0.01	79 ± 0.01	–
	0.5	0.64 ± 0.02	68 ± 0.02	–
	0.7	0.53 ± 0.02	57 ± 0.02	–

As this model was trained exclusively on 2021 imagery, its transfer to imagery acquired in other years sees a drop in prediction accuracy. Although this is not quantified here, Figure 3 visibly shows extensive *FN* in predictions made on the 2010 imagery, particularly over large and dense stands. This is linked to its apparent spectral difference to the 2021 training imagery, potentially caused by sensor difference or capture earlier in the year. In contrast, the similar appearance of 2018 and 2021 imagery sees good visual performance in scenarios of both rush cover increase (Figure 3a) and decrease (Figure 3b). In the more recent imagery, *FP* errors sometimes occur in very dark shadow. Importantly, model transferability can be increased by adding additional supervised examples of areas where performance is poor, for instance by supplementing here with training data from 2010 and 2018 imagery, particularly of dense stands of rush.

Figure 3 Prediction examples of fields with overall (a) increase and (b) decrease rush cover (threshold=0.5). Extents are provided in Figure 4. Tiles are 1.8 km wide.

Disregarding 2010 data due to poor model transferability, we find a small (< 2%) decrease in rush cover between 2018 and 2021. Parcel-level changes in rush cover are mostly < 5% in magnitude (Figure 4), likely representing noise related to model accuracy error rather than meaningful change, but there are areas both of substantial increase (e.g., Figure 3a), generally occurring at higher elevation where active management is less likely, and substantial decrease (e.g., Figure 3b), most likely caused by management.

Figure 4 Change in rush cover of improved grassland parcels between 2018 and 2021 (threshold=0.5). Upper insets provide the extent of tiles shown Figure 3.

Model transferability errors notwithstanding, we have shown that rush can be automatically detected on high resolution aerial RGB imagery by CNN, where supplied with sufficient training data. As this approach is faster and more scalable than both field survey and manual remote sensing survey, it is likely that rush distribution results, summarised at field-level, can be used to target and improve management, for example by contributing to more accurate costing estimates for herbicide application.

In addition to replicating our method elsewhere in the UK, future research should engage with farmers to validate findings of substantive rush cover changes and explore their relationship to management practices. Alongside investigation of climatic data, this could help to better understand the mechanisms driving rush expansion and could ultimately lead to the development of a predictive model. There is

also opportunity to extend our approach using imagery of higher spatial and spectral resolution. This could increase segmentation accuracy relative to at 0.25 m resolution, where the edge pixels of rush are spectrally mixed with grassland or ground. Such improvements are increasingly being achieved using unoccupied aerial systems (UAS), which also provide flexibility over survey timing and capture instrument, for example facilitating the use of hyperspectral or light detection and ranging (LiDAR) data that could increase the distinction of rush from improved pasture, albeit at the expense of spatial coverage (Kattenborn *et al.*, 2021). More broadly, the problem of detecting fuzzy and amorphous continua is not unique to rushes, and as such future work exploring the automatic detection of similar fuzzy environmental objects could benefit from the bespoke metrics of detection and segmentation accuracy presented here, especially where present in smaller abundance than their surroundings.

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Biographies

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